

TEACHING THE SCIENCE OF “EDUCATION” IN IMPROVING SPIRITUAL EDUCATION

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Abstract: The article provides an understanding of the content of the concepts of spirituality and education. The issue of teaching the subject "education" in the improvement of spiritual education is also investigated.

Keywords: education, innovation, pedagogy, spirituality, society, modernization.

ПРЕПОДАВАНИЕ НАУКИ “ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ” В СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИИ ДУХОВНОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ

Аннотация: В статье дается понимание содержания понятий духовности и воспитания. Исследован также вопрос преподавания предмета "воспитание" в совершенствовании духовного воспитания.

Ключевые слова: образование, инновации, педагогика, духовность, общество, модернизация.

INTRODUCTION

At the new stage of Uzbekistan's development, attention to youth education is rising to the level of state policy. On August 23, 2019, under the chairmanship of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, the importance of education and upbringing was discussed at the meeting of the video selector dedicated to the issues of developing the public education system, increasing the qualifications and influence of pedagogues in society, and raising the spirituality of the young generation. At this meeting, the Head of State spoke about the upbringing and morals of the young generation and said, "School is a matter of life and death, a matter of the future. This issue cannot be solved by the state, government and governors themselves. This should become the work and duty of the whole society. It is impossible to change a person and society without changing the school," he said.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

"It is necessary to strengthen the foundations of spiritual education in the continuous education system. "There is no break in education" we often repeat the deeply meaningful saying. But, unfortunately, this rule is not being followed in the organization of spiritual and educational activities. In this regard, the fact that the kindergarten, school, higher education, neighborhood system is working separately, that is, the lack of mutual cooperation and harmony has a negative effect on the effectiveness of our work" [1.285.]. Therefore, at present, the school is not only a place of knowledge, but also a place of raising spiritual education. The need to pay great attention to spiritual education is increasing. One of the reasons for this is that a clear system should work in the educational work of the school.

In fact, for many years, education has turned from education of children into an additional burden performed in free time - a secondary job, and has become a long-term process, and the pedagogical culture of the society has decreased, and the pedagogical and psychological knowledge of preschool education, school pedagogues, and parents about education is insufficient to meet the requirements of the time. did not give [2.]. The complications of mistakes made in

education are widely discussed in everyday life, mass media, and social networks, and are the cause of public protests.

RESEARCH RESULTS

If the school system is taken as a tool of the strategy of spiritual education, "...the process of spiritual education in the general secondary education system includes two periods:

the first period - at the age of 7(6)-10 years - in primary classes;

the second period - in the period of 11-17 years old - in middle and upper classes.

The state educational standard of general secondary education and curricula form age-appropriate basic spiritual and moral virtues (competencies) in students - loyalty to the Motherland, entrepreneurship, willpower, ideological immunity, kindness, responsibility, tolerance, legal culture, innovative thinking, hard work" [3.], is marked as. This means that it is a means of forming the basic spiritual education of young people. In our opinion, in this process, first of all, it is possible to raise all sources of spiritual experience of students, the relationship between children in the community, the relationship between students and their teachers and parents, and the aesthetic levels of everyday life. Secondly, the correct correlation of activity and education forms at different age stages is ensured. Thirdly, it is expressed by the inclusion of ethical criteria in the assessment of all types of activities and the manifestation of the personality of students without exception.

Means of spiritual education in the school system include general and private methods and forms. One of the methods of spiritual education is to educate students in the moral sphere. At the same time, qualities such as entrepreneurship, willfulness, ideological immunity, kindness, responsibility, tolerance, legal culture, innovative thinking, hard work are formed, which serve to form students' knowledge about moral standards and values. Another method of spiritual and moral education is to involve students in activities, that is, it is necessary to provide spiritual education in physical work, socially useful, artistic-creative, educational and cognitive, sports and recreational processes. "Education is our future, a matter of life and death. Therefore, we have no right to delay reforms in this area. As complicated as it may be, we need to lay the foundations of schooling today. Because we have lost a lot of time"[4.], which means that the school system is very important for society. The decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the measures to introduce the science of "Education" in general secondary educational institutions step by step" [5.] was drawn to the attention of these young people. As defined in it, "Taking into account the age and psychophysiological characteristics of students of general secondary educational institutions, to inculcate universal human values and high spirituality in their minds, to educate them in the spirit of patriotism and humanitarianism, to organize spiritual and educational work in general secondary educational institutions on a new basis" it can be noted that it was introduced.

Based on the conditions of today's intense time, we can observe that the attention to education and upbringing is increasing in the world. At the new stage of Uzbekistan's development, attention to the issue of education is expected to reach a new stage. Because the introduction of Education makes it more important for pedagogues-teachers teaching in schools to be able to use different methods of teaching, to learn new pedagogical technologies, to be aware of the general and specific principles of teaching methods of Education. This means that the use of modern pedagogical technologies in teaching based on the tools of the spiritual education strategy increases the effectiveness of achieving the intended results.

As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan stated in his Address to the Oliy Majlis, "...it is important for all of us to acquire modern knowledge, to become the owner of true enlightenment and high culture" [6.]. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the priority directions of systematic reform of secondary and out-of-school education, raising the spiritual, moral and intellectual development of the young generation to a new level in terms of quality, and introducing innovative forms and methods of education into the educational process have been set as a goal[7.].

DISCUSSION

The issue of continuous education is being raised to a new level after the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 31, 2019 No. PQ-1059 "On approval of the concept of continuous spiritual education and measures for its implementation". In this decision, tasks related to the effective implementation of tasks related to the education of the population, especially the youth, the necessity of their spiritual education, and its impact on the development of our country are clearly indicated.

One of the motivating factors for educating today's young people to become perfect people, to form their spiritual growth, is to educate the growing young generation to be spiritually healthy and mature. In the implementation of this task, the necessary need for effective use of modern pedagogical technologies is to make the means of spiritual education strategy an important issue in the field of education, to restore our national values, to realize our identity, to form a national idea and ideology, and to restore the place and respect of our holy religion in our spiritual life. to continue with is to raise them to a new level and strengthen their effectiveness.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, Jadidist Abdulla Awlani said about raising a spiritual person in his views: "People who acquire good qualities are called good people." When Awlani means good people, he means brave people who can do good to people, humble, generous, hard-working, compassionate, knowledgeable, and care for others, then "Bad people are called people whose bad qualities outweigh good qualities" [8.12.] emphasizes. And this is done through important scientific means of raising spiritual education.

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